

TECHNOLOGY OF FORMING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCES IN STUDENTS WITH HEARING DEFECTS IN PRIMARY CLASS READING LESSONS

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Abstract: In this thesis, there are opinions about the technology of formation of communicative competences in students with hearing impairment.

Key words: Special education, reading lesson, linguistic unity, communicative competences, didactic support, differential and individual approach.

Introduction:

One of the main tasks of special education is the social adaptation and integration of children with disabilities in psychophysical development into society. It is known that any defect in a child's physical and mental development affects his general development and causes other defects. Disturbance of the auditory analyzer leads to significant disturbances in the speech and general development of the child. One of the necessary means of increasing the effectiveness of the correction-development process in the work of a teacher-defectologist is the search and application of new pedagogical technologies of education.

One of the goals and tasks of preschool education, which the state and society put before the primary education organization, in addition to forming knowledge and skills, is a favorable condition for opening and developing the child's opportunities and realizing his innate abilities - is to create conditions. The changes taking place in society today require rapid adaptation to new conditions.

Hearing impairment has a negative impact on the development of thinking in children with hearing loss, but their intelligence is preserved at any age. So, the potential possibilities of a deaf child are the same as those of a normal hearing child. The implementation of these opportunities is not limited to arming with knowledge, skills and abilities, but is achieved in a specially organized educational process aimed not only at the development of hearing and speech,

but also at the formation of the entire cognitive activity. According to L.S. Vygotsky, "the problem of deafness in society is a social problem."¹

The use of information and communication technologies is of particular importance in the process of education and social rehabilitation of deaf and hard-of-hearing children with specific communicative characteristics. This factor is also strengthened by the fact that visual perception of information takes the leading place in connection with the compensatory activation of the preserved sense organs in hearing impaired children. In increasing interest in knowledge, one cannot rely only on the content of the studied material, methods of involving children in the educational process and training technologies are important. Computers and computer technologies have become an integral part of our lives.

In the process of education, it is sometimes difficult to explain any learning material in words to a hearing impaired child. With the help of multimedia tools, it is easier for children to perceive the necessary information. In addition, new information technologies that make it easier to change the volume, in particular, by changing certain frequencies of audio materials, can be used in exercises to develop auditory residuals. When working with hard of hearing and deaf children, information and communication technologies are used for the following purposes:

- increase learning motivation;
- increase the efficiency of the educational process;
- to help activate the cognitive sphere of children.

One of the advantages of using information technologies in teaching is to increase the quality of education due to the novelty of training, interest in working with computers. The use of information and communication technologies makes it possible to conduct classes at a high aesthetic and emotional level, provides visibility, in necessary cases, more didactic material can be used, saves time, allows each child to work at his own pace, forms independent activity skills, allows the defectologist to work individually with the child in a differentiated manner, provides an opportunity to quickly control and evaluate educational results.

Children are interested in any activity involving modern technologies and have a positive attitude. This helps to increase their motivation and achieve results that are important for both the child and the teacher. The computer allows to create conditions for increasing the effectiveness of the educational

¹ Выготский Л.С. Мышление и речь. Психологические исследования / Л.С. Выготский. – М.: Лабиринт, 1996.416 с.

process, opens wide opportunities for the development of new education, and adapts to the individual characteristics of the child.

One of the most important results of innovative work in our primary education organization is training using information and communication technologies. In primary education, computer technologies can be used in almost all activities. The teacher teaches the children that the computer is not only for games.

Thus, it helps the teacher-defectologist in his work. This is expressed by the ability to create, systematize, and store an electronic database of text and visual materials, individual tasks, and certain educational materials, methodological developments. Through information and communication technologies, the possibility of independent activity expands and real research activity skills are formed. Access to various information systems, electronic libraries and other information resources is provided.

In addition, using information and communication technologies, a teacher-defectologist can apply special educational programs of a corrective and developmental nature in teaching children with special needs. In special education, the following programs have been created for the development of children's speech culture, socio-emotional spheres: "Мир за твоим окном", "Видимая речь". Programs are exploratory in nature, developing a wide range of skills and imagination. However, the lack of such programs in Uzbek for children of preschool and junior school age with hearing impairment remains an urgent problem.

The creation of excellent electronic programs and mobile applications for the development of the speech, social-emotional and cognitive areas of children with hearing impairment by Uzbek specialists working in the IT field not only facilitates the work of deaf educators, but also allows parents to engage with their children through such programs and applications can create motivation for them to perform the tasks given by the teacher without difficulty.

During the course of the lesson, students perform tasks that are perceived only by hearing or hearing and sight, answer questions, study texts relying on hearing, sight or hearing perception, learn to write dictation by hearing. From the beginning to the end of school education, students are always taught to listen and perceive new and unfamiliar speech material by pronunciation.

Scientific studies conducted by defectologists L.S. Vygotsky², R.M. Boskis and others made it possible to determine the historical development of speech and the development of their cognitive sphere.

In some children with hearing loss, the hearing ability of the third degree is determined, as in deaf people, but at the same time it is noted that not only low, but also medium frequency sounds can be perceived. It is difficult for a deaf child to communicate with the people around him because of external influences and poor communication with the environment. Mental activity of such children is simple, their reactions to external influences are less and varied. The characteristics of the psyche of a hearing-impaired child develop differently compared to children with hearing ability. This feature should be taken into account when organizing education and training of children with hearing impairment. The researches of T.G. Bogdanova, E.G. Rechitskaya, T.V. Rozanova³ and others showed that one of the main problems in the development of cognitive processes in children with hearing impairment is low concentration and stability of attention.

The specific features of the development of attention in deaf children are due to the fact that visual perception is of great importance for them, and the main burden of processing incoming information falls on the visual analyzer. Lip reading requires full concentration on the face of the person speaking, perception of dactyl speech to the position of the fingers. These processes are possible only with the constant attention of the deaf child. Therefore, deaf children tire more quickly than normal hearing children. Deaf children have difficulties in switching attention, which means that children need more time to explain the content of information, which leads to a decrease in the speed of the performed activity. In this regard, various visualization tools are used in the education and upbringing of hearing impaired children. In working with such children, the deaf pedagogue should use information and computer technologies, which will allow them to feel comfortable in new socio-economic conditions.

Multimedia classes conducted on the basis of computer educational programs allow combining audiovisual information presented in various forms (video, animation, slides, music), stimulate children's voluntary attention due to

² Выготский Л.С. Мышление и речь. Психологические исследования / Л.С. Выготский. – М.: Лабиринт, 1996.416 с.

³ Григорьева Т. А. Особенности познавательной деятельности детей с нарушением слуха. Учебно-методическое пособие. Минск, 2005

the possibility of displaying events and objects. Possession of computer technologies allows to increase the flow of information on subject content and methodological issues thanks to electronic carriers and information available on the Internet.

It is no secret that the material that is interesting to the child is well absorbed. Multimedia presentations make it possible to present training and development material as a system of live informational images filled with fully structured information in an algorithmic order. In this case, different channels of perception are involved, which makes it possible to store information not only factually, but also in an associative form in children's memory.

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